

12th UIC WORLD CONGRESS ON HIGH-SPEED RAIL
8-11 July 2025 - Beijing, China

HIGHSPEED

中国 · 北京 · 2025

**Innovation and Development
for a Better Life**

MultiModX

An approach for the
strategic and tactical evaluation
of multimodal networks

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6.3 Intermodality & Multimodality

Introduction – Towards a multimodal transport system

The role of rail in the multimodal air transport network

- ▶ Direct substitution/competition/complementarity
- ▶ Feeder/Distributor from hub
- ▶ Increasing catchment area

Complex interaction driven by passengers!

Door to Door

Strategic considerations

Scheduling phase

Network-wide impact

- ▶ Passenger behaviour when changes to system

Tactical considerations

Day of operations

Tactical management of passengers

- ▶ Ensuring connectivity

Modelling multimodal networks

Need for an evaluation framework!

MultiModX

Multimodal Performance Framework

Digital catalogue of indicators

- ▶ Passenger-centric
- ▶ Open

KPAs and example indicators

- ▶ Operational Efficiency
 - Pax processing time
 - Total journey time
 - Buffers in itineraries
 - Missed connections
 - ...
- ▶ Interoperability
 - Modal share
 - Infrastructure connectivity
 - ...
- ▶ Flexibility
 - Diversity of destinations
 - ...
- ▶ Cost-Efficiency
 - Load factors
 - ...
- ▶ Capacity
 - Demand served
 - Catchment area
 - ...
- ▶ Environment
- ▶ Predictability

Strategic (scheduling phase) Multimodal Evaluator

Strategic Evaluator

Policy packages

Policy Package	Name	Description
PP00	Baseline	- Multimodal connections allowed
PP20	Multimodality enforced	- Integrated ticketing - CO ₂ tax for aviation - Short-haul flight ban

Demand served between regions

PP00

Strategic Evaluator

Policy packages

Policy Package	Name	Description
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Demand served between regions

PP20

Strategic Evaluator

Policy packages

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Total mobility time

Total mobility time from ES511 to NUTS3 regions for PP00

Strategic Evaluator

Policy packages

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Infrastructure connectivity

Egress
PP00

Strategic Evaluator

Policy packages

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Infrastructure connectivity

Egress
PP20

Strategic Evaluator

Policy packages

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Infrastructure connectivity

Strategic Evaluator

Replanning of networks in disruptions

HSR Barcelona – Madrid Closed (PP00)

Alternatives for affected passengers

Tactical (day of operations) Multimodal Evaluator

Tactical (day of operations) Multimodal Evaluator

Mercury

- ▶ Agent-Based Model for air transport
- ▶ Extended to include rail and passenger connection processes

Tactical Evaluator

Evaluation of fast-track at airports

- Connectivity between rail and air at Madrid

Delay in rail-to-airport connection

- Fast-track to reduce kerb-to-gate times

Conclusions

MultiModX provides

- ▶ Multimodality performance framework (passenger-centric focus)
 - Passenger-centric
 - Open digital catalogue of indicators
- ▶ Strategic (planning) Multimodal Evaluator
 - Assess policies / scheduling / infrastructure
 - Replanning of networks
 - Passenger behaviour driven
- ▶ Tactical (day of operations) Multimodal Evaluator
 - Materialisation of network
 - Passenger-centric metrics
 - Evaluate mechanisms support multimodality

MultiModX

<https://multimodx.eu/>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101114815>

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Thank you
for your attention

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